

Experiment on Phototaxis Behavior of Barnacle Larvae

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Abstract. To many larvae of biofouling organisms, phototaxis behavior was crucial for their survival. Research on the phototaxis behavior of many of them was done, however the comparison of phototaxis behavior of two similar species was not enough. This experiment compares the phototaxis behavior of the larvae of subtidal acorn barnacle in the genus *Balanus* collected from Dapeng Shenzhen and the larvae intertidal stalk barnacle *Capitulum mitella* towards six different wavelengths of light source. The result of this experiment showed that despite being different species, the two specimens share similar positive phototaxis behavior towards blue and green light, which supports the idea that when two closely related species living in highly contrasting environment, despite living in different environment, the larval phototaxis behavior will also be similar.

1. Introduction

For many relatively advance organisms, phototaxis behaviors are crucial to their survival in nature. These behaviors allow them to tract food source, avoid predators, and also function as indicators for time of reproduction. Phototaxis behavior is basically the sense and reaction to light, which could be either moving towards the light source, avoiding the light source, or no reaction. In order for the phototaxis behavior to occur, the organisms need to have visions that can sense light.

Barnacles are marine sessile crustaceans and composed a large portion of the organisms in the biofouling community. Their life cycle includes four major stages: firstly, the nauplius stages and secondly the cyprid stage, both stages have locomotion ability, and when the cyprid stage comes to the end, the larvae will search for a place to attach and metamorphose into juvenile barnacles. Unable to move and covered with a calcified shell, they feed on planktons by obtaining them with their fans-like limb.

Figure 1. The acorn barnacle *Balanus* sp.

A. Adult of *Balanus* sp. attached on the oyster in the biofouling biome.

B. the nauplius larva of *Balanus* sp.

The first target specie (Fig 1A) for this experiment belongs to the barnacle genus *Balanus* in the family Balanidae of the subphylum Crustacea. They are very large genus (the type of the family Balanidae) of barnacles comprising the sessile acorn barnacles and including littoral and deep-water forms. Some of these species cause destructive fouling on ships and on underwater cables^[1]. The larvae of these barnacles are shown in Fig. 1B. The sampling site for *Balanus* barnacle's adult located at Dapeng in Shenzhen at a biofouling biome. The GPS coordinate are 22°34'04.2"N 114°31'52.0"E. The salinity was 3ppt and the pH was 8.

The second target species was *Capitulum mitella* (Fig. 2A), more commonly known as

gooseneck barnacle. This species is widely seen in the Japanese sea and sometimes Asian Subtropical and Tropical coastline. Unlike most barnacles, *C. mitella* have a scaled stalk that attach to the surface instead of the shell directly. They had 8 pieces of scale that protect the mouth part. Their larvae are shown in Figure 2B. The *C. mitella* used for this experiment comes from the lab culture, which were cultured in conditions similar to where they live in nature including light, salinity, pH and temperature.

Figure 2. *Capitulum mitella*:

A. adult of the *Capitulum* sp. alone; B. the nauplius larva of *Capitulum mitella*

All specimens use for the experiment were nauplius larvae. The main goal of this experiment is to test the hypothesis that the larvae of these two completely different species may have the same phototaxis behavior, for example positive phototaxis towards blue and green light. Although these two specimens are genetically and structurally different and live in very different environments, they do in a certain period of their life cycle shares similar living conditions. I hypothesize that such conditions may result in different organisms to develop the same behavior.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Experimental Settings

The sampling site for adult *Balanus* barnacles is located at Dapeng in Shenzhen at a biofouling biome. The GPS coordinate are 22°34'04.2"N 114°31'52.0"E. The salinity was 30ppt and the pH level was 8. In order to bring the live adult, sometimes the samples were collected with bivalves or other fouling organisms that they are attached to. The

samples were then transported to the lab within 90 minute and were kept in an oxygen-rich environment for a night. Throughout this process, sample were put in weak light condition to prevent larvae from releasing.

The adult samples were then shot with a light source from a side of the container in order to induce spawning, and the visible planktons that were attracted by the light were transferred to the first petri dish by a pipette. Then the larvae went over 4 petri dishes to get rid of other species. By using the method of dilution, the final product, which was 25ml with a concentration of 10 individuals per milliliter, are put into a 3cm*3cm*15cm rectangular transparent container (Fig. 3). The sample was then put under an infrared light generator with a stand on top if it which hold an iPhone 13. The whole set up was put in a dark environment.

Figure 3. The experimental setup for this experiment.

When doing the experiment, fully charged laser pointers with wavelengths of 532nm, 405nm, 635nm, 515nm, 650nm and 445nm were set up one by one on a smaller stand. The activated laser was point to the 3cm*3cm side of the rectangle. The recording was then immediately begun and the action of the larvae within 150 seconds was record. After each test, the sample was gently stirred and left for a minute without being interrupted.

The same process was used for the stalk barnacle nauplius larvae, except the concentration of larvae was 8 individuals per milliliter due to not enough samples.

2.2. Data Analysis

The acquired video data was then analyzed based on the density changes in the 5cm area near the light source. The 3*3*5cm area in front of the light source was recorded to see how many larvae are in this area using the following procedure. The data was recorded for every 30 second. The process was done 5 time using different frames within the time range and the medium was obtained to ensure accuracy. Detail example can be showed in Fig. 4.

If the trend of the number of larvae in that area was increasing, it was concluded that the larvae showed positive phototaxis behavior to that wavelength of light. If the trend of the number of larvae in that area was decreasing, it was concluded that the larvae showed negative phototaxis behavior to that wavelength of light. If the number of larvae in that area had no clear trend, it was concluded that the larvae showed no phototaxis behavior to that wavelength of light.

Figure 4. An example of how the data was recorded.

3. Results

The result of this experiment shows that for both the larvae of *Balanus* and the *Capitulum mitella*, phototaxis behaviors exists and shared common traits. When exposed to laser with wavelengths of 405nm, the *Balanus* sp. and a slight increase from 3 to 14 individuals

from 30s to 150s; the *Capitulum mitella* had a relatively greater increase in number which is from 4 to 19 individuals (Fig. 5). On the other hand, the larvae of both species had shown significant activities when exposed under lights with wavelengths of 445nm, 515nm, or 532nm. Under these lights, the number of individuals swam toward the light source reached a peak of 19 individuals for *Balanus* sp. and 37 individuals for *Capitulum mitella*. When exposed to lights with wavelengths of 635 nm and above, both specimens shown no clear trends in the number of individuals appeared near the light source.

Figure 5. All data obtained from both specimens in the form of graph,
with *Balanus* sp. larvae on the left and *Capitulum mitella* larvae on the right

In conclusion, both species shown positive phototaxis behavior towards the lights with wavelength from 405 to 532 nm and no reaction to lights with wavelengths that are above 635 nm. However, the larval specimens of *Capitulum mitella* had shown a stronger phototaxis behavior to the light source compared to the larvae of *Balanus*. Yet still, the overall trait of the two specimens remained the same (Fig. 5).

4. Discussion

Despite the two specimens varies a lot in size and structure as well as their adult habitats, the nauplius larvae of two species had both shown positive phototaxis to blue and green light and shown no response to red light. It is generally believed that the same larval response to light occurs in many other biofouling organisms, because what determines their phototaxis behavior was their environment (Fig. 6). The nauplius larvae of barnacles are like all other mesoplankton that drift along with currents. Thus, the phototaxis behavior of barnacles will be similar to the species that have visions and live in the same condition. According to Wendt and Woollacott (1999), the phototaxis test on the larvae of bryozoans, also a type of biofouling organisms but in a very different taxon, the larvae of *Bugula neritina* are positively phototactic on emergence from the brood chamber^[2]. Even though bryozoan are completely different species from barnacles, the phototaxis behavior are almost matched since their larvae share the same environment as they are all planktonic larval stage.

Figure 6. Light penetration in most sea water matches the data obtained in the experiment.

Something worth mentioning is that also, the phototaxis behavior of barnacles' and other biofouling organisms' larvae may differ as they go through different stages in their lifecycle. Since most adult barnacles are located in places without strong sunlight, it is possible that when cyprid larvae may show negative phototaxis behavior. To find out, more experiments on the phototaxis behavior of different larval stages in barnacle life cycle are needed to be done. For example, the cyprid stage of different barnacle species may be put to test since they live in different environments. In summary, this study reported the larval phototaxis behavior of two barnacle species, and the result shows that the larvae have similar behavior possibly due to similar living environment at a certain period of their life cycle.

References:

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